

Preparation, investigation and characterization of polysilazane-derived (oxy)nitride coatings on steel substrate

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ABSTRACT

In this work the effect of different treatment such as sandblasting, etching on the surface or combination of these method and preparation of the coatings by dip coating and spray coating method with different volume fraction of commercial or manufactured materials is under investigation. The main goal of the treatment of steel is choose the best type of cleaning stainless steel and avoid the spallation of the base coat from the steel substrate. Stainless steel (AISI 441) was used as basic substrate. Before pre-treatment and coating process, the steel plates were cut into required dimension 1.5 cm × 1.5 cm, cleaned by six different ways. The experimental conditions of the pre-treatment of stainless steel are shown in the Tab. 1. The surface morphology and roughness parameters were observed by Raman spectroscopy with the use of the Renishaw InVia using atomic force microscope. After the pre-treatment of stainless steel follow the preparation of coatings.

PHPS (perhydropolysilazane) and Durazane 1800 (both Merck KGaA, Germany) were used like pre-ceramic precursors. In order to obtain dense and adherent coatings with sufficient protection, new types of glasses (Schott AG, Mainz, Germany) and ceramic fillers (YSZ – Inframat, USA, AYZ20) were used. The pre-treated substrates were dip-coated (Relamatic RDC 15, Switzerland) in the PHPS solution to obtain the bond-coat. The curing of the PHPS bond-coat was carried out in air at 450 °C for 1h with heating rate of 3K/min (N41/H, Nabertherm, Germany). The subsequently applied top coat was prepared by mixing defined volume fractions of a liquid polysilazane HTT1800, ceramic filler particles and glasses. Parameters like the filler and glass systems, the volume fraction of the components were varied to optimize the composite coating system. The pyrolysis of the coatings was performed in air at the temperature 850 °C with a holding time 1 h. The compositions are listed in the Tab. 2 and Tab. 3. After the pyrolysis the compositions were in detail analysed by SEM, XRD.

Tab. 1: Experimental conditions of pre-treatment of stainless steel

Shortcut	Pre-treatment of stainless steel
U	3-steps ultrasonic vibration cleaning in acetone, ethanol and deionized water (10 min)
P	Sandblasting with glass beads (70-110µm), ultrasonic cleaning
N	Chemical etching – NITAL (ethanol+nitric acid), 1min
K	Chemical etching – KROLLS REAGENT (distilled water, nitric acid, HF), 20sec
P+N	Sandblasting with glass beads + etching with NITAL
P+K	Sandblasting with glass beads + etching with KROLLS REAGENT

Tab. 2: The selected compositions with Schott glass G018-281 and precursor AYZ20

COMPOSITIONS	HTT1800 (vol. %)	YSZ (vol. %)	G018-281 (vol. %)	AYZ20
D1	20	20	40	20
D2	25	20	35	20
D3	30	20	30	20

Tab. 3: The selected compositions with Schott glass G018-281

COMPOSITIONS	HTT1800 (vol. %)	YSZ (vol. %)	G018-281 (vol. %)	YSZ:GLASS
C1a	20	50	30	5:3
C1b	25	46,88	28,12	
C1c	30	43,75	26,25	
C1d	35	40,63	24,37	
C2a	20	40	40	1:1
C2b	25	37,5	37,5	
C2c	30	35	35	
C2d	35	32,5	32,5	
C3a	20	30	50	3:5
C3b	25	28,12	46,88	
C3c	30	26,25	43,75	
C3d	35	24,37	40,63	

The surfaces and morphology of samples after treatment (Fig. 1a) shows that different etching and sandblasting on the stainless steel surface created different size of roughness and there is a relation between surface morphology and the kind of used reagents. It was found that pre-treatment of the substrate surface was very important for successful preparation of bond coat. Sandblasting and etching with different chemical etchants rendered the different substrate surface roughness. Atomic force microscope measurements revealed the surface roughness of sandblasted and etched stainless steel, ranged from 0.2-1.7 μm that related to ultrasonic cleaning and sandblasting, respectively. It was found that ultrasonic cleaning showed the best adhesion of PHPS to the steel (Fig. 1b).

In the case of top coat in all cases was found that addition of smaller amount of polymer HTT1800 (<30 vol. %) was not effective and spallation of top coat from bond coat was observed. With the high amount of polymer the adhesion of bond coat and top coat was good. The composite coating D3 (Fig. 3c) provides the most promising overall results. The top coat D3 was prepared with 30 vol. % of HTT1800, YSZ, and powder precursors ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-Y}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$) as passive fillers and the glass system G018-281 as sealing agent. After a thermal treatment in air at 850 $^\circ\text{C}$, the resultant coating with the thickness up to 40 μm is almost fully dense, with no cracking or delamination and it is expected to prevent the access of aggressive environment to the steel substrate at temperatures up to 1000 $^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 1: Surfaces and cross-sectional SEM images a) sandblasted surface of steel, b) composition C3cU – ultrasonic cleaning, c) compositions D3U

Keywords: bond coat, PDC coatings, top coat, treatment of steel

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the the grant APVV 0014-15 and European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.